

Hybrid Networked/Live Performance, Listening, and Composition: Renewing the Concert Ritual

Marc Ainger and Ann Stimson

The Sonic Network Arts Project

Columbus, Ohio

<https://sonicarts.squarespace.com>

ainger.1@osu.edu

Abstract

Hybrid networked/live music performance (henceforth designated as “hybrid music performance” in this paper) is an emergent form that has become increasingly common and accessible. Hybrid music performances include both remote and in-person performers and an in-person audience, as well as the possibility to host remote audiences.

In this paper, we will consider recent networked/live performances, specifically, the [Sonic Networked Arts Performances in Vienna in 2023](#). We will consider these performances through the lens of recent ideas from the discipline of the philosophy of technology, specifically employing the concept of the “in-between.” We will suggest that the increased number of mediation technologies, along with the increased multiplicity of listening/viewing points engendered by hybrid performances invites the creation of new forms of concert presentation and reception.

1. Hybrid Music Performance

Music is multimodal and includes multiple points of perception. However, because hybrid music performance often contains many more layers of mediation than other forms of musicking, there is a corresponding proliferation of points of perception. A web of inter-related yet unique sonic and visual immersive environments branch into ever more portals of experience, crossing barriers of time and space, communities, and cultures. The inclusion of additional mediation such as live electronic processing of acoustic instruments; cross-adaptive practice (Baalman, Emmerson, Brandtsegg: 2018, 86); various spatialization techniques; and the juxtaposition of live and remote performers, compounds the number of ways one may experience the event.

Hybrid music performance incorporates a mixture of transparent and obscure sound sources, rapid shifts of listener and performer focus and mode, and a “spooky interaction at a distance” (Lewis: 2020) in virtual and physical space. Scholars in the discipline of the philosophy of technology have written about “the in-between” - that liminal space that is both digital and physical. It is this space that hybrid music performances inhabit. The in-between is a creatively enacted space, inviting exploration and invention.

2. The SNAP Concerts as an example of hybrid music performances

The Sonic Network Arts Performance (SNAP) concerts were a series of immersive multi-channel hybrid in-person/remote events, the first of which took place in April 2023 in the Klangtheater of the Universität für Musik und darstellende Kunst Wien.

The SNAP concerts joined “in-person” performers with remote performers from various locations in the US and in Europe, using video and low latency, high quality uncompressed sound across the internet. The software programs that we used included Jacktrip for sound, and vdo.ninja for video. The performances took place in a multichannel ambisonic space with 24.4 speakers for an “in-person” audience, and also for an audience that could join from anywhere, live-streamed on the internet. The concert was also simultaneously live-streamed to the [Earth Day Art Model](#) festival, a separate event that was being streamed online at the same time. In sum, many simultaneous events resulted from a single concert.

The SNAP concerts joined performers from California (Stanford’s CCRMA); Minnesota (Zeitgeist); Florida (Sonic Arts); Germany (Berlin Technical University); Belgium (the Orpheus Institute); the Linz Anton Bruckner Privat Universitat; and Vienna (mdw Klangtheater).

Network audio and video were handled by Mike O’Connor (The Haven, Wisconsin), using a complex infrastructure that was developed for these events.

Figure 1. Locations of performers

Figure 2. Audio and video production

3. Multiple Points of Perception

There is an old joke about a retired orchestral double bass player. As a member of the bass section, much of what he played consisted of an alternating “do” to “sol.” After retirement he returns to visit his colleagues and sits in the audience for the first time to listen to a concert. His fellow bassists ask him what he thought of the concert. He marvels, “I never noticed before but there are these beautiful melodies that the violins are playing at the same time we are playing.” Ridiculous but resonant, this joke highlights the differing perceptions throughout the orchestra.

The conductor, the instrumentalists, and the audience each have a unique experience based on their location, the hall, and their immediate surroundings. The conductor adjusts tempo and expression based on their sense of the venue. Different characteristics of live spaces produce different acoustics. Even the number and temperament of bodies in the hall can change the resonance and clarity.

In hybrid music performance, on the other hand, multiple layers of mediation from technology; from multiple spaces; and from multiple time zones, branch into a dense web of intertwined points and layers of perception. This web of intertwined points produces new viewpoints: in-person listener, remote listener, in-person performer, and remote performer. These roles continuously overlap. A remote performer is both an in-person listener and a remote listener; an in-person performer is both an in-person listener and a remote listener; an in-person audience is also a remote audience. A remote listener is listening to performers who are reacting both remotely and “in-person.”

4. The in-between

One way to think about some of the possibilities of this web of relationships is to consider the concept of the in-between - the liminal space that is in-between the digital and physical. The in-between, a current subject of inquiry in the philosophy of technology, is discussed by Yoni van den Eede. He writes:

... either technology may appear as transparent: one does not consciously perceive aspects of the technology as such.... Or it may appear as opaque: the technology or some of its aspects come clearly in view but may perhaps be blocking the perception of certain other things. In some cases, both features may be present at the same time, in an interrelated sense.... It's here. And it's not here. It's in between us. (Eede: 2011, 141 and 157)

In his seminal book on the philosophy of technology, *Technology and the Lifeworld: From garden to earth*, Don Ihde notes ‘The closer to invisibility, transparency, and the extension of one’s own bodily sense this technology allows, the better.’ (Ihde: 1990, 74).

If we apply this to hybrid music performance, we know that every performer has a camera, and a microphone for input; and speakers/headphones, and a screen for output. The video is good, though compressed quality; the quality of the audio is uncompressed, better than CD quality. In fact, the audio is such high quality that it sounds as though the performer is with us in the room, amplified through the house system.

Leaving aside the issue of latency for a moment, when I am in Vienna and the cellist is in California, am I seeing and hearing approximately what I would be seeing and hearing if I were

in California with the cellist? In Don Ihde's terms, how close to invisibility, transparency, and the extension of one's own bodily sense are we?

Ihde, however, further elaborates on this idea of transparency, stating: 'desire (for transparency) is at best contradictory and illusory, for it (secretly) rejects what technologies are: the technological mediation actually has transformative effects - it cannot be wholly transparent.' (Ihde: 2008). Yoni van den Eede also notes, 'A technology itself can have intentionality too.' (Eede: 2011, 149)

So, another way of posing the transparency question is to replace "seeing/hearing" with "experiencing". The question then becomes this - if the cellist were on stage with us in Vienna would we all be having the same experience that we are having when we are in Vienna and the cellist is joining us remotely from California? The answer to this question is obviously "no." It would be a different experience.

Robrecht Vanderbeeken, in his article "Screen as In-between"

...refutes the apparently innocent, common sense idea that the audio-visual screen is just a window to the world that displays an extra set of sensual data alongside and independent of our personal, unmediated experience of reality. On the contrary, the screen as an in-between is both a mediator and generator of reality that eventually compromises the distinction between us and our environment. (Vanderbeeken: 2011, 245)

Expanding on this idea, Vanderbeeken continues:

... the fundamental tension is of a different order. The combination of the natural perception of reality, the mediated perception of reality through the screen and the familiarity with realms of simulacra results in the perception of reality as a hyperreality. This inevitably impedes a return to unmediated perception... but it does not imply that hyperreality is mere semblance in the form of an inflated and overdone version of reality. On the contrary, experiencing hyperreality can just as well be an intensified and thus a very real experience in which exploration, recollection and imagination come together and open up new dimensions of perception that would not otherwise be possible. In this sense, hyperreality is the experience of a kind of super-reality in which a plenitude and diversity of reality are present. (Ibid: 2011, 252)

If we think of the in-between as a space in its own right, and, as a creatively enacted space, "a generator of reality"; a space that can be thought of as "an intensified and thus a very real experience in which exploration, recollection and imagination come together;" then we open ourselves up to a situation where we can consider hybrid music performance as an opportunity to rethink and renew our ideas of what performance could be.

Hybrid music performance is not a traditional concert plus new elements, nor is it an impoverished event that lacks the presence of some of the performers. It is a new and different space that welcomes us to reconsider our old notions and to imagine new ones.

5. Conclusion

The institutions of music and art are conservative, and many of our concert rituals derive from late 19th and early 20th century practice. Hybrid music performance invites us to reconsider these rituals and these notions by considering the implications of the specific characteristics of the form.

Hybrid music performance incorporates a mixture of transparent and obscure sound sources, rapid shifts of listener and performer focus and mode, and interactions across time and space. Therefore, performers and audiences must continually renegotiate their roles in and outside of real-time. The number of roles that both performers and audience members inhabit simultaneously proliferate with the number of mediation and perception points in hybrid music performance. Just as each performer will have a unique experience, each audience member will also have a unique experience, and that experience can change from moment to moment.

Time and space in any concert is ephemeral and liminal. Clock time exists simultaneously with many other perceptions of time. We anticipate the next event, we make sense of past events retroactively. This is also the case in hybrid music performances, but here there are many additional factors. The performers and the audience are literally occupying many different time zones, spaces, and communities simultaneously during the performance. As we approached midnight in Vienna, we could see the afternoon sun travel across the room in California.

Technology is never transparent or neutral. It has its own intentionality, and our awareness of this can open us up to new ways of considering its possibilities. If we think of the in-between as a space in its own right, and, as a creatively enacted space, “a generator of reality”; a space that can be thought of as “an intensified and thus a very real experience in which exploration, recollection and imagination come together;” then we open ourselves up to a situation where we consider hybrid music performance as an opportunity to rethink and renew our ideas of what performance is and what it can become.

6. References

BAALMAN, Marije, EMMERSON, Simon, BRANDTSEGG, Øyvind. “Instrumentality, Perception and Listening in Crossadaptive Performance.” The 4th International Conference on Live Interfaces (ICLI), 14-16 June 2018, Porto, Portugal, ICLI, 2018.

EEDE, Yoni van den, “In Between Us: On the Transparency and Opacity of Technological Mediation”, *Foundations of Science*. 16, 2011, p. 139-159.

IDHE, Don, *Ironic Technics*, Copenhagen, Automatic Press/VIP, 2008.

IDHE, Don, *Technology and the Lifeworld: From Garden to Earth*, Bloomington, Indiana University Press, 1990.

LEWIS, George, “Spooky Interaction at a Distance: Telematic Afrofuturism.” *The Disappearance of Music*, Dec. 7, 2020, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=cDvIsV0bxsc>.

VANDERBEEKEN, Robrecht, ‘The Screen as an In-between’, *Foundations of Science*, 16 (2-3), 2011, pp. 245-257.